

EFFECT OF PANCHVALKAL KWATH PRAKSHALNA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DUSHTA VRANA: A SINGLE CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Dustavrana are a frequently occurring problem in current period produced commonly as a complication of trauma and it causes long lasting problem to the patient. According to *Sushruta*, a *Vrana* converts to *Dushtavrana* due to excessive vitiated doshas caused by improper management by Physician or Patient himself. *Dustavrana* is an excessively damaged condition characterized by vitiation of *Mamsa*, *Medha Dhatus* and *Dosha* and caused by external injuries with exudation of *Durgandhayukta Puyam* (pus), temperature, pain, inflammation, itching, redness and also oozing of *Durgandha-yukta raktam* with no intention to heal. The management of Non healing wound with ayurvedic methods is one of the major areas of the research and has wide scope of study. In the present study treatment methods like *Vrana Prakshalana*, *Dhoopan* and *Bandhana* were done which is mentioned by *Acharya sushrutha* in the context of *Vrana Shasti Upakrama*. This is the case report of a 70year old patient, who presented with an open ulcer on the posterior aspect of the right fore arm associated with pain, slough, discharge and foul smell. *Prakshalana* with *Panchvalkal Kwath*, *Dhoopan Karma* and *Bandhana Karma* with *Jatyadi tail* for 10 days along with internal medication was given as the line of treatment which showed remarkable results.

KEYWORDS: *Dustavrana*, *Dhatus*, *Shasti Upakrama*, *Panchvalkal Kwath*, *Dhoopan*, *Bandhana Karma*.

INTRODUCTION

Shalya Tantra, the classical branch of ancient Indian Surgery, describes various types of wounds and their management. several times, non-healing wounds are posing difficulties in surgical practice. Healing of wound is a natural process; but due to the interference of vitiated *Doshas*, *Vrana* becomes *Dushta* and normal healing process gets delayed.^[1] The word *Vrana*(wound) is imitative from the verbal root “*Vrana*” which means anything that produces break or discontinuity of the skin and deeper tissues beneath it^[2] which is described in detail in *Susrutha Samhitha*.^[3] *Vrana* is classified into two types^[4] i.e. The first is *Sharira Vrana*, which develops due to the disturbance of internal *Doshas*. The second is *Agantuja Vrana*, which arises from external causes such as trauma. If the *Vrana* (wound) gets infective or fails to heal over a prolonged period, then it is known as *Dustavrana* (infected wound or (Nonhealing ulcer).^[5] Currently, clinicians administer medicines such

as Betadine, Silver Nitrate, Hydrogen peroxide, Eusol, or Antibiotics, along with other internal medications commonly used in medical practice. But these treatments have their own limitations and has to rely on available life-saving procedures like amputation or surgery. According to *Acharya Sushruta*, the management of *Vrana* (wounds) involves sixty distinct therapeutic measures, collectively known as *Shashti Upakrama*.^[6]

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate the efficacy of *Panchvalkal Kwath Prakshalana* followed by *Vrana Dhoopan Karma* & *Jatyadi Tail* topical application in the management of *Dushta Vrana*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

CASE REPORT

A 70 years old non- diabetic, non- hypertensive male patient, came to *Shalya Tantra* OPD of RD Memorial

Ayurveda P G College & Hospital, Bhopal (MP) with the complaints of a large sized wound with pain, discharge, itching, slough and foul smell, in the posterior aspect of the right fore arm. The complaints were associated with bilateral pedal edema for 15 days.

Patient was having a history of insect bite over posterior aspect of right forearm, followed by development of cellulitis over that area. He consulted physician for the treatment of the same and underwent local dressing along with oral medications (unknown) for 15 days but there was no improvement in his condition.

History of Present Illness

Patient was apparently alright 25 days ago. Then he noticed swelling over right forearm after an insect bite. Then the swelling got aggravated and developed into an ulcer after few days. He consulted local physician for the treatment of the same and underwent daily local dressing along with oral medications (unknown) for 15 days but the condition did not resolve.

Then the patient came to Shalya Tantra OPD of RD Memorial Ayurveda P G College & Hospital, Bhopal (MP), for further management.

Past History

No previous history of Hypertension, Diabetes Mellitus, Bronchial Asthma etc.

Personal History

General condition: fair
Bowel: Regular

Treatment Given

Bahya chikitsa

Sr.No.	Vranopakrama	
1	Vrana Prakshalana	Panchavalkala Kashaya
2	Vrana Dhoopana	Gugguladi Varti
3	Vrana Vikeshika & Bandhan (Wound dressing)	Jatyadi tail

Abhyantara chikitsa

Sr.No.	Drugs	Dose
1	Mahamanjisadi Kwath	15ml BD
2	Varunadi Kasaya	15ml BD
3	Vilwadi Gutika	1 TDS
4	Kaishora Guggulu	1 TDS

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

The patient's progress was evaluate on the basis of subjective and objective criteria by assigning the suitable score to each parameter.

The method adopted for scoring was as follow:

Subjective criteria

1) Pain

Sr no.	Symptoms	Score
1	No Pain	0
2	Localized feeling of pain during movement only but not during rest	1

Sleep: Sound
Appetite: Good
Addiction: Alcohol & Smoking

Examination

Inspection

Site – Posterior aspect of the right forearm
Size- 18X 10 cm
Edge – Punched out edge
Floor-Slough /Unhealthy granulation tissue present
Surrounding skin- Hyperpigmented
Discharge – Sero-purulent discharge
Odour- foul smell present
Tenderness- Present.

Investigation

All routine investigation (CBC, ESR, RBS, LFT etc.) done and were within normal range.

Materials required

Panchavalkal Kwath, Dhoopan varti, Jaytayadi tail, Sterile cotton, sterile pads, Gauze pieces, Roller bandage, Artery forceps, Curette, Scissors.

Method of application

Initially wound debridement was done to remove the slough tissues over the wound with curette, followed by cleaning with Hydrogen Peroxide and Betadine solution. Surrounding area was cleaned with Surgical spirit. Then Panchavalkal Kwath Prakshalana was done for 20 min followed by Vrana Dhoopana Karma with Vrana Dhoopana Varti. Wound dressing was done with Jatyadi tail using sterile gauze and pads.

3	Localized feeling of pain during rest but not disturbing sleep	2
4	Localized continuous feeling of pain, radiating & not relieving by rest	3

Objective criteria

1) Smell

Sr no.	Smell	Score
1	No smell	0
2	Foul smell	1
3	Tolerable unpleasant smell	2
4	Foul smell which is intolerable	3

2) Colour

Sr no.	Colour	Score
1	Pinkish red	0
2	Slight red	1
3	Reddish Black	2
4	Pale yellow/ Blackish	3

3) Discharge

Sr no.		Score
1	No discharge/ dry dressing	0
2	The gauze is slightly moist	1
3	After opening the bandage, the gauze is completely wet	2
4	The bandage moist completely within 24 hours	3

RESULTS

S.No.	Assesment Parameters	Before Treatment 0 day	After treatment 1 st day follow up	5 th day Follow up	10 th day Follow up
1	Pain	3	2	0	0
2	Smell	3	2	1	0
3	Colour	3	2	1	0
4	Discharge	3	2	1	0

Before treatment

After Treatment 1st Day

DISCUSSION

Acharya Sushruta described the treatment of *Vrana* according to the different stages of wound healing. In the present case, three of the *Shashti Upakramas* were utilized — *Vrana Prakshalana*, *Dhoopan*, and *Bandhana*^[7] — as part of the therapeutic approach.

Vrana Prakshalana: *Vrana Prakshalana* using *Panchavalkala Kwath*^[8] helps in cleansing (*Shodhana*) and healing (*Ropana*) of the wound. As *Kwath* was lukewarm it promotes vasodilatation there by promoting better healing of the wound.

Vrana Dhoopana – *Dhoopana* with *Varti* prepared from ingredients such as *Guggulu*, *Agaru*, *Sarjarasa*, *Vacha*, *Sarshapa*, *Haridra*, *Nimbapatra* etc. being very subtle it is able to reach deeper channels and convey the therapeutic qualities of all the substances used. These drugs act as *Krimighna*, thereby reducing foul odour.

Dhoopana has been described to exhibit antiseptic, insecticidal, antipyretic, and anti-inflammatory effects.

Vrana Bandhan – *Vrana Bandhan* with *Jatyadi Tail* is considered useful in the management of *Dushta Vrana*. The ingredients of *Jatyadi Tail* predominantly possess *Tikta* and *Kashaya Rasa*, along with *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna*. Because of these properties, the formulation helps in pacifying *Pitta* and *Kapha* and shows actions such as *Vrana Shodhana*, *Ropana*, *Pootihara*, and *Vedanasthapana*.

Internal medications which were administered helped in reducing *Shotha*, *Dosha dushti*, and *Rakta dushti*, *Visha* and by enhancing wound healing with improvement of general condition of the patient.

CONCLUSION

This case study demonstrates that *Dushta Vrana* can be effectively managed through a holistic Ayurvedic approach. Cleansing of the wound with *Panchavalkala Kwath*, followed by *Dhoopana* using *Gugguladi Varti* and *Bandhana* with *Jatyadi Taila*, together with appropriate oral medications, contributed to complete healing of the lesion.

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